

VIRTUAL MUSEUMS AND THEIR ROLE IN DEVELOPING INFORMATION-ANALYTICAL COMPETENCE IN FUTURE HISTORY TEACHERS

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Abstract

This article provides information about the "interactive multimedia software product that displays museum collections in electronic form" as part of a modern innovative program designed to connect future history teachers with the activities of the virtual museum and increase their knowledge of the history of our country. In addition to the fact that it helps the process of acquiring new knowledge about history and culture, popularizes cultural institutions and expands the reach of the target audience, in addition to the scientific and educational impact, such a platform can increase the tourist attractiveness of the region and provide additional funds for the development of the cultural sector of the region. It is justified that it creates the necessary conditions for attraction.

Key words: virtual museum, "unofficial" museum resources, traditional museum expositions, virtual tours, historical thinking, virtual 3D tours, virtual tours, museology, platform region, museum collections, interactive multimedia software product.

INTRODUCTION

The travel habits of the Uzbek people are not very well formed. This can be attributed to the fact that the material condition of most people was not good, as well as the fact that such habits were not formed until recently. The Uzbek people can spend all their wealth and money on weddings and building a modern house, but they consider sightseeing, travel, and pilgrimage to be of the next level. In order to bring the future history teachers who think with such a worldview to a new life, way of thinking, and way of living, it is necessary to introduce them to the global cultural environment, to enable them to learn about other people's way of life and views of life through travel, and to create a new society. is one of the important tasks in

In higher education, state museums play an important role in educating future history teachers on the basis of historical memory, in making them loyal and responsible to the motherland. After all, "to the young generation the feeling of carefully preserving national clothes, jewelry, work tools, old household items created by the labor of our ancestors in the past and looking at them with respect if we can inculcate them, it is possible to make them a humane person

with a truly national faith, who respects our values. Museums perform a huge pedagogical task as a scientific and educational institution that collects, preserves, organizes and studies historical, material and spiritual monuments" [6:200]. That is why it is one of the important tasks to connect future history teachers with the activities of the virtual museum, to increase their knowledge about the history of our country.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Presenting information about cultural objects in the form of "virtual museums" is a great opportunity to refer to the past to the present in a new way. Scientific research in this direction is of great importance, because culture is not a new tool, but new values[1:98].

Virtual museum is understood as "an interactive multimedia software product that displays museum collections in electronic form." In world practice, the term "virtual museum" appeared in the 1990s. At the time, it was used to describe "informal" museum resources[5:80]. The purpose of creating virtual museums is not to reproduce the original in detail, but to convey the general concept of the cultural object. Currently, virtual platforms have the opportunity not only to repeat the expositions of traditional museums, but also to expand the capabilities of real cultural institutions. Providing the possibility of virtual visits to museums through the Internet simplifies knowledge. The process of acquiring new knowledge about history and culture helps popularize cultural institutions and expands the reach of the target audience. In addition to the scientific and educational impact, such a platform creates the necessary conditions for attracting additional funds to increase the tourist attractiveness of the region and develop the cultural sector of the region[3:41]. Today, virtual museums can be not only a way of presenting information about cultural objects, but also an entertainment, educational and socializing tool.

D.S. Vasilina, A.A. Denikin, T.YE. Maksimova, A.M. Korotkov, D.V. Zemlyakov, YE. V. Ivanov, A. V. Shtirov, K. Y. Milovanov, A. A. Vinokurova, Y. D. Vyatkina, J. Kh. Ismailova, M. S. Mukhamedova have developed effective methods of organizing the scientific creativity of students, developing the process of scientific creativity in the system of continuous professional education, as a virtual museum as a modern cultural phenomenon. .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Virtual museums are places that serve to increase historical, artistic, aesthetic and scientific literacy. They reflect the history, culture, development and crisis of societies. An interesting display of exhibits with traces of different

eras, histories and societies has a great intellectual and emotional impact. In the virtual museum, it is possible to witness the clash of eras, societies, thoughts and ideas based on new approaches[4:90]. In modern life, it is necessary to deviate from the traditional tasks and functions of museums and implement more extensive programs that help them to actively participate in the life of society. Therefore, the creation of virtual museums using innovative technologies that serve to develop informational and analytical competence of future history teachers, and creating a new way of traveling through history based on them, will give effective results.

Such as "Museology and archival studies", "Historical geography", "State history of Timur and the Timurids", "Epigraphy of the peoples of the world", "Historical local studies and urbanization processes", which are transferred to students of the "History" major in the higher education system. organization and improvement of subjects on the basis of virtual tours gives future history teachers the opportunity to see a fragment and preserved part of history with their own eyes and to see their theoretical knowledge and imagination in real reality. This increases students' enthusiasm and interest in studying history in depth, as well as the desire to travel to these places and their emotional ability.

A virtual museum is a type of website that displays museum materials. The advantage of virtual museums is that they use Internet technologies to store, protect, and widely, quickly and easily present exhibits to the public.

Virtual museums are not only a cultural and educational institution, but also a collection of world art treasures that allow virtual viewing of exhibitions of great interest to students. Their role in the development of historical thinking in general high school students is great. Because, unlike real museums, virtual museums can be visited by students independently without the help of a teacher. So, it gives them a lot of opportunities. This not only develops historical thinking, but also serves as a basis for enriching the spiritual world of students.

The use of virtual museums allows students not only to familiarize themselves with museum exhibits, but also to develop their informational and analytical competence [2:201-203].

The following can be noted as unique opportunities of the virtual museum of the cultural heritage of the CIS countries:

- Possibility to create virtual museum halls that do not exist in the real world;
- Ability to create virtual 3D tours combining various exhibits located in different countries within one tour;

- An opportunity to get to know the historical and cultural heritage of peoples through virtual tours combining various exhibits;
- Possibility to create virtual tours of historical and cultural centers, monuments, regions [7].

"Virtual excursions" - different from real museum excursions, give students the opportunity to make a virtual trip to museum funds. In this, they can organize trips to museums that they cannot see in real life.

By traveling to virtual museums, students understand the historical roots of spiritual heritage, and understand historical, literary, and artistic examples as a whole, integrated spiritual heritage. Therefore, the organization of independent work of students with virtual museums through the help and guidance of the teacher requires wide promotion of museology in science programs. This will lead to certain changes in the educational programs. It is very effective to carry out such work.

The current state and problems of the pedagogical process aimed at organizing virtual historical tours for the development of informational and analytical competence in future history teachers are as follows:

First, the higher education institution should develop a practice of connecting its educational and non-educational activities, pedagogical practices with the organization of virtual historical tours. For this, it is necessary to try to improve the quality of education in the pedagogical process, as well as to launch cultural and entertainment projects. Higher education, in fact, is a place that prepares students for life and gives them the opportunity to try themselves in various fields and show their inner talent. An educational institution should train students for years, while improving their knowledge, guide them to various types of activities, help them achieve their desires. However, today's higher education system of Uzbekistan works towards a very narrow goal. It tries to educate students to memorize a certain information base, to be disciplined and obedient. That's why graduates of higher education, even though they are educated, cannot be creative, adaptable to the situation, think in a new way, and have high information-analytical competence. They can be an assistant who performs the task correctly, accurately and on time, but they will not become innovators. Therefore, based on the requirements of today's time, the role of organizing virtual historical trips in educating future teachers as innovators is considered high. Because virtual historical trips give the student a strong incentive to rediscover and self-realize. At the same time, it forms a desire to engage in tourist activities.

Secondly, virtual museums and their pedagogical possibilities are being evaluated as the most effective way to direct students to virtual historical tours in HEIs. However, the use of virtual museums or organizing trips to virtual museums in higher education has not been started. Future history teachers are formed in the practice of organizing virtual historical tours or in other educational processes. The activities of museums related to history, nature or techniques and technologies existing in Uzbekistan are naturally connected with the activities of some higher educational institutions. Therefore, it is necessary to organize virtual historical tours, and at the same time, it is necessary to use a strong speaker, a knowledgeable and creative person in the museum pedagogy.

Thirdly, in the system of higher education, it is necessary to develop mechanisms for using a new methodology of imparting knowledge to students. As a passive listener, it is possible to learn, acquire knowledge, introduce them to real-life situations, changes and shortcomings in the field, and aspects that need to be innovated, without relying only on textbooks and literature. Giving is highly effective. Because connecting science and practice is one of the urgent problems of today. Museum pedagogy is important for this. Because virtual museums are a place to show the genesis, development trends and perspectives of a certain field, and allow them to see, understand and feel them.

CONCLUSION

Virtual museums are characterized by the use of interactive features provided by electronic media: the user can "move" through three-dimensional halls, get any information and images. Another important aspect is providing constant feedback to site visitors.

The implementation of the virtual museum leads to a positive solution to the priority issues in the development of informational and analytical competence in future history teachers;

Students will be able to understand the personal and social nature of the structure, size, size, compositional construction, field of application, importance of archaeological exhibits of different historical periods;

in the course of training, provision of a high level of visuality and interactivity, increase in the effectiveness of developing students' visual, analytical, independent thinking based on museum materials, the establishment of an axiological approach to historical reality is achieved in them;

organization, management, acceleration and control of collaborative learning activities of students on the basis of conducting virtual trips will have a positive effect.

References:

1. Василина Д.С. Виртуальный музей как феномен современной культуры // Международный журнал исследований культуры. № 3. 2016. – С. 96-101.
2. Винокурова А.А. Виртуальный музей как инновационная форма гражданско-патриотического воспитания младших школьников / А.А.Винокурова, Н.Д.Неустроев // Меридиан. – 2018. – № 4 (15). – С. 201-203.
3. Коротков А.М., Земляков Д.В., Иванов, Е.В., Штыров А.В. Виртуальные музеи как часть единой образовательной информационной среды // Вестник академии детско-юношеского туризма и краеведения. № 4. 2013. – С. 40-43.
4. Максимова Т.Е. Виртуальные музеи: функции сохранения «современности» / Т.Е. Максимова // Исторические, философские, политические и юридические науки, культурология и искусствоведение. Вопросы теории и практики. – 2013. – № 7-2 (33). – С. 89-91.
5. Максимова Т.Е. Виртуальные музеи: аналитический обзор зарубежных публикаций // Вестник Московского государственного университета культуры и искусств. № 4. 2015. – С. 79-83.
6. Ходжаев Б.Х. Умумтаълим мактаби ўқувчиларида тарихий тафаккурни модернизациялашган дидактик таъминот воситасида ривожлантириш. Педагогика фанлари бўйича диссертацияси. – Тошкент, 2016.
7. <https://www.xabar.uz/madaniyat/Virtual muzey. U qanday ishlaydi?>

